

Tsallis Entropy is No Longer Linked Maximum Probability if $q \neq 1$?

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In the case of Boltzmann's entropy, $-k \ln(\text{number of states})$, there is a physical principle of maximizing the number of states subject to a priori constraints. This is equivalent to maximizing probability which yields Shannon's entropy, i.e. probability for large $N = \text{Product over } i \text{ } p_i^{\text{power } N}$ $(N p_i) \rightarrow \ln(\text{probability}) = N \text{ Sum over } i \text{ } N p_i \ln(p_i)$. Maximizing probability or the number of states seems to be equivalent to minimizing information subject to a priori constraints. Thus, there is a clear informational condition to both Boltzmann and Shannon's entropy.

Here we argue that this minimal informational feature no longer seems to hold for Tsallis entropy. We have argued in previous notes that there are physical examples of an a priori constraint: $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i p(e_i)^{\text{power } q}$. We also argued that Tsallis entropy follows from maximizing a mathematical function: $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } p_i^{\text{power } q} F(p_i)$ such that: $F(p_i) = -e_i/T$ and $p_i^{\text{power } q} d/dp_i F(p_i) = \text{constant}$. For $q \neq 1$, extremizing this function is no longer equivalent to extremizing probability (minimizing information). As such, it remains a math procedure unless there is a physical reason why $p_i^{\text{power } q} d/dp_i F(p_i) = \text{constant}$ should hold, we suggest.

Boltzmann and Shannon Entropy

Boltzmann's entropy is: $S = -k \ln(\text{number of states})$ ((1))

If one maximizes the number of possible states subject to a priori constraints, one minimizes information. Thus, there is a clear informational foundation to the idea of maximizing this entropy.

Shannon's entropy (which is consistent with that of Boltzmann) is also based on such a clear minimization of entropy or maximization of probability. If one has a set of probabilities p_i and tosses a die, so to speak, $N \gg 1$ times, one expects $N p_i$ outcomes of i :

Probability(N tosses) = $\text{Product over } i \text{ } p_i^{\text{power } (N p_i)}$ ((2a)) or

$\ln(\text{Probability}) = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } N p_i \ln(p_i)$ ((2b))

((2b)) is the negative of Shannon's entropy. Maximizing it subject to a priori constraints means minimizing information.

At the same time: $\ln(p_i \text{ unnormalized}) = -e_i/T$ ((3a)) and $p_i d/dp_i \ln(p_i) = \text{constant}$ ((3b))

In other words, one has the two conditions ((3a)) and ((3b)) which are completely consistent with minimization of information.

We have suggested in previous notes that one may generalize ((3a)) and ((3b)) to obtain Tsallis entropy (such that $q \rightarrow 1$ yields Shannon's entropy), but such a math generalization no longer seems to minimize information, which seems to be a key idea in statistical mechanics.

Physical Example of a Probability $p(e_i)$ power q

Tsallis entropy seems to follow from the presence of q , i.e. the introduction of a new AND probability $p(e_i)$ power q . If $p(e_i)$ is normalized, $p(e_i)$ power q is not. As a physical example, one may consider $p(e_i)$ to equal the probability that a sunflower seed is not eaten by a bird in a day. If such a seed takes q days to germinate, then $p(e_i)$ power q is the probability that it germinates. (Here one assumes that it germinates if not eaten.)

Extremization of a Math Function Subject to A Priori Constraints to Obtain Tsallis Entropy

We have shown in previous notes that one may follow the math forms of ((3a)) and ((3b)), namely:

$$F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad ((4a)) \quad \text{and} \quad p(e_i) \text{ power } q \, d/dp(e_i) F(p(e_i)) = \text{constant} \quad ((4b))$$

to find a function $F(p(e_i))$. This is in fact $\ln_q(x) = \{x \text{ power } (1-q) - 1\} / \{1-q\}$ ((5))

Then, Tsallis entropy is a math function:

$$\text{Sum over } i \, p(e_i) \text{ power } q \ln_q(p(e_i)) \quad ((6))$$

such that its extremization subject to $\text{Sum over } i \, p(e_i) = 1$ and $\text{Sum over } i \, e_i p(e_i) \text{ power } q = E$ yields \exp_q , the Tsallis distribution. For $q=1$, $\ln_q = \ln$ and $\exp_q = \exp$.

The point we wish to make is that even though one extremizes a math function subject to constraints, one no longer seems to extremize probability or minimize information.

Maximization of Probability

We note that ((2a)) should hold for any probabilities with $N \rightarrow$ infinite, even for $p(e_i)$ power q . The problem is that in the recipe of the above section, \ln and not \ln_q appears, but:

$$\text{Product over } i \, \{p(e_i) \text{ power } q\} \text{ power } (N p(e_i) \text{ power } q) \quad ((7))$$

$$p(e_i) \text{ power } q \longrightarrow \exp\{ -q \ln(p(e_i)) \} \quad ((8))$$

In other words, simply because $q \neq 1$ appears does not mean that \ln becomes \ln_q when writing probability. It seems that:

$$\{N p(e_i) \text{ power } q\}^{-q} \ln(p(e_i)) \quad ((9))$$

is the entropy linked with extremizing probability or minimizing information. ((8)) does not yield Tsallis entropy, suggesting that Tsallis entropy does not minimize information.

Extremizing ((3)) subject to $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)^q = E$ yields:

$$\ln(p_i) p_i^{q-1} - e_i/T - C_1 p_i^{q-1} = C_2 p_i \quad ((10))$$

This does not yield the Tsallis \exp_q , but does yield the Maxwell-Boltzmann result for $q=1$.

As a result, the key feature ((4b)) in extremizing a math function to obtain Tsallis $\ln_q(p(e_i))$ is not associated with minimizing information. This begs the question: Is there a statistical reason for using ((4b)) or is one simply finding a math function which when extremized yields a particular distribution \exp_q ? Given that this is not the minimal information solution, what is it?

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that even though one may find a math function which when extremized subject to a priori constraints, $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)^q = E$, namely $\sum_i p(e_i)^q \ln_q(p(e_i))$, this function no longer minimizes information except in the $q=1$ case. As a result, it is not clear what specific statistical viewpoint is taken when using Tsallis entropy as it is not the minimal informational result, it seems.